

FREEDOM AND SAFETY CONCEPTS IN THE CHILD'S INTERPRETATION (A CASE STUDY OF THE CHARACTER OF PIERRE NOZIÈRE)

Radchuk O. V. (Kharkiv, Ukraine)

<http://orcid.org/0000-0002-0343-6796>

Abstract

The study reveals the process of developing such abstract concepts as FREEDOM and SAFETY in the mentality of a preschool child. For an adult, these concepts are relevant and significant all lifelong. The research is based on an autobiographical work of a well-known French writer Anatole France that is entitled “Pierre Nozière” and is made up of several short stories united by their content. Anatole France managed to create a character of a child by focusing on young children psychological traits. Several times, the writer compares a young child and a nestling. Analogies are observed in two aspects: a free bird vs a captive bird and a chick in a nest vs an abandoned chick. According to these contrasts, corresponding abstract concepts are developed in little Pierre’s consciousness. For the boy the concept of SECURITY is equal to the concept of HAPPINESS. The formation of the concept of FREEDOM is not clear-cut in the mind of the inquisitive child: although he longs for freedom, he understands that if there are no limits, then danger will arise. Such generalizations are made by the results of the analysis of the psychological characteristics of communicative and other activities of Pierre Nozière, those cognitive and emotional-volitional processes that influenced the formation of the child's personality.

Key words: the concepts of FREEDOM and SAFETY, child psychology, Anatole France, Pierre Nozière, character.

Anatole France opens the autobiographical work “Pierre’s Book” with the dedication, for which the words of Dante Alighieri from the “Divine Comedy” were chosen as the epigraph: “Having passed half of my life...”. The writer was forty years

old at the time, when he decided to recreate his memories of his early childhood in an artistic form. The words of the Italian educator seem to have become prophecies: Anatole France died shortly after the solemn celebration of his 80th birthday. But everything he kept in his memory, he managed to transfer to the pages of novelettes, which he combined into a book dedicated to the growth of Pierre Nozière. The writer aptly notes that “memory is a miraculous power, and that the gift of resurrecting the past is as wonderful, even more precious, than the gift of predicting the future” (France, 1987, p. 7).

In the autobiographical work, the recovery of reminiscences is represented episode by episode, at first as individual fragmentary memories, which gradually increase in volume, content, and experienced emotions. Anatole France shows the physical growth of a boy named Pierre and reveals the child's mental, emotional, and intellectual development. The author draws attention to the thirst with which the boy strives to learn about the environment. The writer is sure that “even the most inexperienced soul instinctively most carefully protects the most precious; because for a child, as for an adult, there is much that is unexplained” (France, 1987, p. 27). Pierre was *a restless questioner*, he was interested in everything around him, he understood in his own way what existence and everyday life were and tried to evaluate everything. Since a person learns the concepts of FREEDOM and SECURITY only over time, children do not feel any restrictions in their actions; unlike adults, they behave naturally freely and do not pay attention to danger. Pierre was a brave, fearless and desperate inventor, as evidenced by such characteristics of the author as *quietly sneaking up*. Growing up in a full-fledged family, harmony and well-being, feeling the love and care of parents every moment, the child felt well protected. We learn about this from the pages of the novelette: *I was happy, I was very happy. I was sure that they would protect me from all evil, and I felt completely safe with them* (France, 1987, p. 21).

In the work under analysis, Anatole France showed the importance of family upbringing in personality formation, the role of father and mother in the development of a child, and the creation of a favourable psychological climate. The writer emphasized that there should be respect and love between all family members. This

was the case in the author's family, and that is why he drew the images of his characters from his nearest and dearest. He, like his main character Pierre, did not hear his parents' quarrels, they always showed mutual respect and tenderness towards each other. Family responsibilities for the household chores and the boy education were divided between the father and the mother. The author puts into Pierre's mouth the words that the parents admired and rejoiced over their child: *Boundless tenderness surrounded me. That's how a nestling is caressed in its feather and down nest* (France, 1987, p. 22). In this context, we observe a vivid and accurate comparison of a child to a nestling. The associative transfer of relations from the world of fauna to the world of people realizes the idea that parental care for a child is a natural phenomenon, that it is necessary to learn from birds how to show decent care for their babies until the chick learns to feed and fly on its own and is able to leave the parental nest. The child feels protected in the family circle and at home, which sets the boundaries between his own vs. someone else's. Modern biologists, physiologists and psychologists conclude that children actively use gestures to define abstract concepts in communication. So, for example, a child's gesture – hands above the head (“I'm at home”) convincingly confirms that the brain centers (areas of the cerebral cortex) controlling speech and hand movements are connected. A child who does not yet know how to speak understands and identifies the concept of SAFETY as being under the roof of the parent's house, in which he is protected. This is not accidental. As we have already explained in our studies earlier, “on the basis of the use of non-verbal signs, the development of the child is activated, they learn the rules of verbal communication and replace gestures with words, which is a consequence of communication with adults” (Radchuk, 2020, p. 18).

Being intelligent and clever, Pierre, although he felt safe, longed for freedom, which for him was limited by the walls of the apartment: *I was doing well. I was doing very well. However, I was jealous of another boy. He was free and brave. From the yard, where he felt like an all-powerful owner, he looked at me through the window like a bird in a cage* (France, 1987, p. 22). And again a comparison with a bird, but with a completely different content. The free flight of a bird is always contrasted with

an enslaved bird in a cage. But freedom is so dangerous. And Pierre understands this and tries to restrain his desire to “free” himself from the care of adults.

From the novelettes of Anatole France, we learn that, for the little boy, the feeling of happiness was still closer to the concept of SECURITY than FREEDOM. A wealthy family invited a nanny for Pierre, who took him for walks and cared for his safety: *Putting my hand in the wrinkled palm of Mrs. Mathias and thus feeling comfortable, I looked around at the harsh power of the surrounding world. There was a deep harmony between the old woman, the dreamy boy and the melancholy suburban landscape* (France, 1987, p. 161). The first violation of the idyll of the universe and ideas about it occurs when Pierre was 6 years old. Suddenly he faced a harsh and even cruel reality. The boy heard a sound that terrified him, later he learned about a terrible event: their neighbour had thrown himself from the top floor of the house. This is discussed in the short story “The Spectacle Merchant”, which has a symbolic title, because we can see better through glasses. Even the things that were invisible. The boy grows up in an instant and begins to think over danger: *Mr. Amosh opened my eyes to the world... He revealed to me that **the earth is big, so big that you can get lost on it, that it is full of incomprehensible and frightening phenomena.** In his presence, life did not seem like a game to me, and I began to understand that there is real suffering on earth. And **that impressed me more than anything else.** Because I finally began to realize that Mr. Amosh was truly unhappy* (France, 1987, p. 157). The assimilation of negative socio-cultural experience by children, its structuring and preservation in individual consciousness greatly affects their psyche, as it is not yet fully formed. Some events, which a person witnesses in their childhood, leave an imprint for the rest of their life, traumatizing the psyche of an individual. Little Pierre Nozière carefully watched the spectacles salesman and, even during his lifetime, reflected on the happiness and unhappiness that were associated in the child's brain with the understanding of freedom and security of life: ... ***I was not sure that they lived under the same beneficent, infinitely happy influence as I did, that they, like me, were protected from all troubles*** (France, 1987, p. 153). So, in his autobiographical prose, Anatole France appears in a new role – that of a children's writer, a teacher and a child

psychologist. Those interesting, full of love and sincere kindness descriptions of the facts of children's behavior, showing relationships with peers and adults, successes and failures in the activities of individuals of different ages demonstrate the writer's knowledge of the peculiarities and laws of children's mental development. The author of the work "Pierre Nozière" emphasizes the importance of a child feeling both free and protected from a very young age, which later transforms into the abstract concepts of FREEDOM and SECURITY.

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